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“SOLID FENCE VS. FULL-VIEW FENCE: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS IN PHYSICAL SECURITY”

In physical security, it is important to consider the design of fence used to protect an asset within the facility or installation. The two general types of fences commonly used – the solid fence and full-view fence. Although they both serve the same purpose of providing barrier to unauthorized persons, but there are significant differences in terms of designs and security impact.

A solid fence is a type of fence designed in such a way the visual access through the fence is denied. Meaning, that outsiders cannot see what is happening inside the facility or installation. This is a major advantage because a potential intruder cannot obtain information about the people, activities, and schedules of the guards assigned to the area. In this way, the chances of spying or surveillance by malicious individuals are reduced. However, it has also a weakness. Since nothing is visible from the outside, it is difficult for guards to observe the environment around the facility or installation. Additionally, a solid fence creates a shadow that intruders can hide in for cover and concealment.

Meanwhile, the full-view fence is constructed in such a way that visual access is permitted through the fence. Its main advantage is that it provides wide visibility for roving patrols and assigned guards. On the other hand, it allows the intruder to become familiar with the movements and time schedule of the guard patrols thereby allowing him to pick the time is advantageous on his part.

Overall, the design of the fence is dependent entirely on the needs of the facility or installation. If the goal is to conceal activities inside the facility or installation, then a solid fence is more appropriate. However, if surveillance and visibility is more important, then a full-view fence is preferable. It is important that every security decision has sufficient basis and analysis to ensure that the facility or installation is safe from the threat of crime or espionage.